

Differences and Relationships in the Learning Styles of Students

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Abstract

Various perspectives on learning styles of students are available based on the results of different investigations. On one hand, the Barsch Learning Style Inventory (BLSI) that consists of 24 statements identifies three learning preferences, namely: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. On the other hand, the Grasha-Reichmann Student Learning Styles Scale (GRSLSS) that consists of 60 statements determines six learning dimensions, namely: competitive, collaborative, avoidant, participant, dependent, and independent. This study aimed to determine the differences and relationships in the learning styles of students using the BLSI and GRSLSS. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions: 1) is there a significant difference among the learning preferences of students based on the BLSI?, 2) is there a significant difference among the learning dimensions of students based on the GRSLSS?, and 3) are there significant relationships between one learning style to every other learning style described in the BLSI and GRSLSS? A sample of 192 students taken from the Bachelor of Science in Cruise Management at John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. enrolled during the first semester of academic year 2013-2014 was considered in this study. Non-proportionate stratified random sampling method, stratified according to year level, was employed in this investigation. A significant difference was found in the learning preferences of the students based on the BLSI. The differences were found between kinesthetic and visual, and between kinesthetic and auditory. Results revealed that the students are both visual and auditory learners. Based on the GRSLSS, significant difference was also found in the learning style dimensions of the students. The differences were found between avoidant and every other dimensions, and between competitive and every other dimensions. Results revealed that the students are more of independent, collaborative, dependent, and participant than avoidant and competitive. Direct relationships exist between one learning style to every other learning style described in the BLSI. Also, direct relationships exist between one learning style to every other learning style described in the GRSLSS. Furthermore, direct relationships exist between kinesthetic and collaborative, and between kinesthetic and participant. Results seemed to suggest that the level of one's being kinesthetic may describe his or her level of being collaborative and participant.

Keywords: learning style, Barsch inventory, Grasha-Reichmann, learning style inventory, reliability

Introduction

Individual differences entail varying preferences. Such reality is manifested across disciplines and group of people, including students. Students, believed as unique individuals, have different preferences in learning. According to Felder (2002), "students learn in different ways".

On how one learns or prefers to process information is what they referred to as learning style. Learning styles may be measured in different ways. Based on the results of different investigations, two perspectives about learning styles are measured using the Barsch Learning Style Inventory (BLSI) and Grasha-Reichmann Student Learning Styles Scale (GRSLSS).

On one hand, the BLSI is a 24-item inventory that assesses one's learning style (Barsch, 1980). The selections, values, and descriptions elicit the three learning preferences, namely: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. Visual learners need to see to know something, have strong sense of color, and may have artistic ability. Nevertheless, they may have difficulty with spoken directions, be easily distracted by sound, and have trouble following lectures. The following are tips in learning for learners of this type: using graphics for reinforcement, color-coding to organize notes and possessions, writing directions, using flow charts and diagrams in taking notes, and visualizing the spelling of words and facts for memorization. Auditory learners prefer listening in getting information. However, they may have difficulty with written directions and inability to read body language and facial expressions. Learning tips for students of this type include: using of tapes for reading and taking of notes, interviewing and participating in discussion, and reading aloud or listening to recordings of test questions and directions. While, kinesthetic learners prefer hands-on, can assemble parts without reading directions, learn better involving physical activities, and may have athletic ability, but may have difficulty sitting still. Students of this type may consider the following in learning: taking consideration of experiential learning, taking frequent breaks during study periods, tracing letters and words to learn spelling and remember facts, using computer to reinforce learning through sense of touch, memorizing or drilling while walking or exercising, and involving some kind of movement while learning (Mathematics Assistance & Learning Lab, n.d.).

On the other hand, the GRSLSS was developed by Anthony Grasha and Sheryl Reichmann. This model is associated with three classroom dimensions: student attitudes towards learning, their views of their teachers and peers, and their reactions to classroom procedures (Grasha, 1996). GRSLSS promotes understanding of learning in a broad context, spanning six categories: competitive, collaborative, avoidant, participant, dependent, and independent. Competitive students learn materials in order to perform better than others in the class; they feel a need to compete with other students for rewards. Among others, students with this style prefer to become a group leader in discussions, be singled out in class for doing good job, and dominate class discussions. Collaborative students feel they can learn by sharing ideas and talents; they cooperate with teacher and peers and like working with others. These students prefer lectures with small group discussion, student-centered aspects of courses, and group rather than individual projects. Avoidant students are not enthusiastic about learning content and attending the class; they uninterested and overwhelmed by what goes in the class. Avoidant learners are generally turned off by most classroom activities, prefer no tests and blanket grades where everyone gets a passing grade, and do not like enthusiastic teachers. Participants are good citizens in the class; they are eager to do as much of the required and optional course requirements. Participant learners prefer discussion, class reading of assignments, and teachers who can analyse and synthesize information. Dependent learners show little intellectual curiosity and they learn only what is required; they view teacher and peers as sources of structure and

support and look for authority figures. Students who are dependent prefer outlines or notes on the board, clear deadlines and instructions for assignments, teacher-centered methods, and little ambiguity as possible in all aspects of the course. Independent learners like to think for themselves and are confident in their learning abilities; they can work on their own but listen to the ideas of others. Students of this type prefer independent study, working alone, self-paced instruction, and student-centered rather than teacher-centered approach (Grasha & Hruska, 1989).

Recognizing the availability of the two inventories and satisfying the curiosity of the researchers on the possible similarities of the said inventories, this study was conducted.

Statement of the Problems and Hypotheses

This study aimed to determine the differences and relationships in the learning styles of students using the BLSI and GRSLSS. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions.

- 1) Is there a significant difference among the learning preferences of students based on the BLSI?
- 2) Is there a significant difference among the learning style dimensions of students based on the GRSLSS?
- 3) Are there significant relationships between one learning style to every other learning style described in the BLSI and GRSLSS?

In line with the aforementioned problems, the following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

- 1) There is no significant difference among the learning preferences of students based on the BLSI.
- 2) There is no significant difference among the learning style dimensions of students based on the GRSLSS.
- 3) There are no significant relationships between one learning style to every other learning style describe in the BLSI and GRSLSS.

Significance of the Study

This study may be beneficial to teachers, students, and researchers.

Teachers may take into consideration the various perspectives about learning style in dealing with their students. They may consider using the inventories in understanding their students. Recognizing the differences of students may help teachers prepare corresponding activities to students of varying learning preferences.

Students may be informed of the various perspectives on learning style and may be confirmed about their possible observations on learning preferences. They may consider measuring their learning preferences using the inventories presented in this study. Understanding the different preferences, they may be guided on how they should attend to their learning.

Other researchers may utilize the results of this study in their future research endeavors.

Delimitation of the Study

The respondents in this study were taken from the Bachelor of Science in Cruise Ship Management students of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. enrolled during the said semester. The data used in this study were collected during the first semester of academic year 2013-2014. Only instruments with complete data were included in the data analysis.

Although mean and standard deviation were introduced, this study focused on inferential analysis using the nonparametric tests, namely: Friedman test, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, and Spearman's rank-order correlation.

Methodology

This study made use of the quantitative-descriptive research design.

Respondents of the Study

The target sample of this study was 200 students from the Bachelor of Science in Cruise Ship Management (BSCSM) of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo) enrolled during the first semester of academic year 2013-2014. Non-proportionate stratified random sampling method, stratified according to year level, was employed in this investigation. However, only 192 students were able to submit the instruments with complete data.

Instrumentation

On one hand, the Barsch Learning Style Inventory (BLSI) is composed of 24 statements (refer to Appendix A). Eight (8) statements correspond to measuring each of the learning preferences, namely: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. Statements number 2, 3, 7, 10, 14, 16, 20, and 22 measure visual preference. Statements number 1, 5, 8, 11, 13, 18, 21, and 24 measure auditory preference. While, statements number 4, 6, 9, 12, 15, 17, 19, and 23 measure kinesthetic preference. Each statement is answerable by often, sometimes, and seldom with the weight of 5, 3, and 1 respectively (Barsch, 1980). The sum of each of the preferences obtained from the responses of every respondent was used in the data analysis.

On the other hand, the Grasha-Reichmann Student Learning Styles Scale (GRSLSS) is composed of 60 statements (refer to Appendix B). Ten (10) statements correspond to measuring each of the learning style dimensions, namely: independent, avoidant, collaborative, dependent, competitive, and participant. Statements number 1, 7, 13, 19, 25, 31, 27, 43, 49, and 55 measure independent dimension. Statements number 2, 8, 14, 20, 26, 32, 38, 44, 50, and 56 measure avoidant dimension. Statements number 3, 9, 15, 21, 27, 33, 39, 45, 51, and 57 measure

collaborative dimension. Statements number 4, 10, 16, 22, 28, 34, 40, 46, 52, and 58 measure dependent dimension. Statements number 5, 11, 17, 23, 29, 35, 41, 47, 53, and 59 measure competitive dimension. While, statements number 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 54, and 60 measure participant dimension. Each statement is answerable by strongly disagree, moderately disagree, undecided, moderately agree, and strongly agree with the weight of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively (Grasha & Hruska, 1989). The average of each of the dimensions obtained from the responses of every respondent was used in the data processing.

Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to present descriptive statistics. Friedman test was used to determine the difference in the learning styles. Wilcoxon signed-rank test served as post hoc test to determine the difference between one learning preference to every other preference described in the BLSI and between one learning style dimension to every other dimension described in the GRSLS. Spearman's rank-order correlation was used to determine the relationship between one learning style to every other learning style described in the BLSI and GRSLS.

Results and Discussion

Difference in the Learning Preferences based on the BLI

Utilizing the Friedman test, a significant difference was found in the learning preferences of the students, $\chi^2(2)=38.958, p=0.000$. Post hoc analysis with Wilcoxon signed-rank tests was conducted with a Bonferroni correction applied, resulting in a significance level set at $p<0.017$. Significant differences were found between kinesthetic and visual ($Z=-5.613, p=0.000$), and between kinesthetic and auditory ($Z=-4.819, p=0.000$). On the other hand, no significant difference was found between visual and auditory ($Z=1.352, p=0.176$). The mean values for both visual and auditory are higher than that of kinesthetic.

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics and the results obtained from conducting the post hoc analysis to determine the difference in the learning preferences describe in the BLSI.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Difference in the Learning Preferences

	<i>M (SD)</i>	Visual <i>Z (p)</i>	Auditory <i>Z (p)</i>	Kinesthetic <i>Z (p)</i>
Visual	26.02 (5.575)		-1.352 ^a (0.176)	-5.613 ^a (0.000)
Auditory	25.51 (5.733)			-4.819 ^a (0.000)
Kinesthetic	23.49 (4.946)			

a. Based on positive ranks

Difference in the Learning Style Dimensions based on the GRSLSS

Utilizing the Friedman test, a significant difference was found in the learning style dimensions of the students, $\chi^2(5)=156.724$, $p=0.000$. Post hoc analysis with Wilcoxon signed-rank tests was conducted with a Bonferroni correction applied, resulting in a significance level set at $p<0.003$. Significant differences were found between avoidant and every other dimension, and between competitive and every other dimension. The pairs with difference are as follow: avoidant and independent ($Z=-8.113$, $p=0.000$), collaborative and avoidant ($Z=-8.436$, $p=0.000$), dependent and avoidant ($Z=-8.223$, $p=0.000$), competitive and avoidant ($Z=-3.737$, $p=0.000$), participant and avoidant ($Z=-8.493$, $p=0.000$), competitive and independent ($Z=-6.699$, $p=0.000$), competitive and collaborative ($Z=-7.544$, $p=0.000$), and competitive and dependent ($Z=-8.293$, $p=0.000$), participant and competitive ($Z=-7.611$, $p=0.000$). On the other hand, no significant differences were found in all other pairs of learning dimensions and these are as follow: collaborative and independent ($Z=-2.849$, $p=0.049$), dependent and independent ($Z=-1.969$, $p=0.049$), dependent and collaborative ($Z=-0.795$, $p=0.427$), participant and independent ($Z=-2.184$, $p=0.029$), participant and collaborative ($Z=-1.904$, $p=0.057$), and participant and dependent ($Z=-0.290$, $p=0.772$). The mean values for independent, collaborative, dependent, and participants are higher than that of avoidant and competitive; avoidant obtained the lowest mean value.

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics and the results obtained from conducting the post hoc analysis to determine difference in the learning style dimensions described in the GRSLSS.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics and Difference in the Learning Style Dimensions

	<i>M (SD)</i>	Independent <i>Z (p)</i>	Avoidant <i>Z (p)</i>	Collaborative <i>Z (p)</i>	Dependent <i>Z (p)</i>	Competitive <i>Z (p)</i>	Participant <i>Z (p)</i>
Independent	3.71 (0.559)		-8.113 ^a (0.000)	-2.849 ^b (0.049)	-1.969 ^b (0.049)	-6.699 ^a (0.000)	-2.184 ^b (0.029)
Avoidant	3.31 (0.669)			-8.436 ^b (0.000)	-8.223 ^b (0.000)	-3.737 ^b (0.000)	-8.493 ^b (0.000)
Collaborative	3.83 (0.575)				-0.795 ^a (0.427)	-7.544 ^a (0.000)	-1.904 ^a (0.057)
Dependent	3.79 (0.532)					-8.293 ^a (0.000)	-0.290 ^a (0.772)
Competitive	3.48 (0.605)						-7.611 ^b (0.000)
Participant	3.79 (0.552)						

a. Based on positive ranks

b. Based on negative ranks

Relationship among the Learning Styles

Utilizing the Spearman's rank-order correlation, strong and direct relationships were found in the following pairs of learning styles: auditory and visual, avoidant and independent, collaborative and independent, dependent and independent, dependent and collaborative,

competitive and independent, competitive and avoidant, competitive and dependent, participant and independent, participant and collaborative, participant and dependent, and participant and competitive. Moderate and direct relationships were found in the following pairs of learning styles: kinesthetic and visual, kinesthetic and auditory, dependent and avoidant, competitive and collaborative, and participant and avoidant. While, weak and direct relationships were found in the following pairs of learning styles: collaborative and kinesthetic, collaborative and avoidant, and participant and kinesthetic.

Table 3 shows the obtained Spearman's correlation coefficients describing the relationships between one learning style to every other learning style described in the BLSI and GRSLSS.

Table 3

Relationships between One Learning Style to Every Other Learning Style

	Visual	Auditory	Kinesthetic	Independent	Avoidant	Collaborative	Dependent	Competitive	Participant
Visual		.770*	.325*	.082	-.007	.095	.106	.056	.087
Auditory			.304*	.037	-.014	.103	.121	.030	.095
Kinesthetic				.136	.080	.148*	.086	.052	.211*
Independent					.535*	.545*	.580*	.673*	.650*
Avoidant						.285*	.339*	.639*	.394*
Collaborative							.661*	.435*	.649*
Dependent								.609*	.619*
Competitive									.544*
Participant									

* $p < 0.05$

Conclusions

The visual and auditory preferences of students are the same, but different from kinesthetic. The levels and differences in the learning preferences seem to imply that the students are both visual and auditory learners; indeed, students may prefer one or more learning styles. On one hand, the results may suggest that students may easily learn where activities are designed for either visual or auditory learners. On the other hand, the results may suggest that these students might require activities designed for both visual and auditory learners to easily learn. These students, however, might have difficulty where learning process involves their body and some kind of movements.

The independent, collaborative, dependent, and participant learning style dimensions of students are the same, but different from competitive and avoidant. The levels and differences in the dimensions seem to imply that the students are more of independent, collaborative, dependent, and participant; indeed, students may possess the same level of different learning style dimensions. The least learning style dimension of students is avoidant. Results seem to imply that students being independent may learn on their own; they prefer self-paced instruction. In addition, results suggest that these students are also collaborative learners; they can work in groups and cooperate with teachers and learners. Further, results revealed that they are

participant learners; hence, they want to take part in learning activities. However, being dependent learners as observed in the results, these students manifest little intellectual curiosity and will only learn things that are required; they prefer teachers providing clear instructions.

Although the amounts of increase are not the same, since direct relationships exist between one learning style to every other style described in BLSI, therefore, as one learning style gets higher, every other style also gets higher. This is also true in the case of the learning style dimensions described in GRSLSS, as one dimension increases, every other dimension also increases. Furthermore, the direct relationships found between kinesthetic and collaborative, and between kinesthetic and participant seemed to suggest that the level of one's being kinesthetic may describe his or her level of being collaborative and participant.

Recommendations

Teachers having difficulty in understanding the behavior of their students in the class may try to administer an assessment of their students' learning preferences. The obtained results would be useful in their preparation of learning activities. Nonetheless, preparing learning activities that consider students of varying learning preferences would be best to ensure the learning of students regardless of their learning style.

Students may try answering the inventories to augment their understanding of themselves. Upon knowing their preferences, they may take into consideration some suggested learning tips for their kind of learners.

Researchers may conduct similar studies involving other variables and taking into consideration other learning style inventories. Further, they may conduct a study about learning preferences and learning activities.

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Appendix A
Barsch Learning Style Inventory

	Often	Sometimes	Never
1 I can remember more about a subject through listening than reading.			
2 I follow the written directions better than oral directions.			
3 I like to write things down or take down notes.			
4 I bear down extremely hard with a pen or pencil when writing.			
5 I require explanations of diagrams, graphs, or visual directions.			
6 I enjoy working with tools.			
7 I am skillful with and enjoy developing and making graphs and charts.			
8 I can tell if sounds match when presented with pairs of sounds.			
9 I remember best by writing things down several times.			
10 I can understand and follow directions on maps.			
11 I do better at academic subjects by listening to lectures and tapes.			
12 I play with keys or coins in your pocket.			
13 I learn to spell better by repeating the letters out loud than by writing the word on paper.			
14 I can better understand a news article by reading about it in the paper than by listening to radio.			
15 I chew gum, smoke, or snack during studies.			
16 I feel the best way to remember is to picture it in your head.			
17 I learn spelling by "finger spelling" the words.			
18 I would rather listen to a good lecture or speech than read about the same material in a book.			
19 I am good at solving and working on jigsaw puzzles and mazes.			
20 I grip objects in hands during learning period.			
21 I prefer listening to the news on the radio than reading about it in newspaper.			
22 I obtain information on an interesting subject by reading relevant materials.			
23 I feel very comfortable touching others, hugging, handshaking, and the like.			
24 I follow oral directions better than written ones.			

Appendix B
Grasha-Reichmann Student Learning Styles Scale

#	Indicator	Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Undecided	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	I am confident of my ability to learn important course material.					
2.	I often daydream during class.					
3.	Working with other students on class projects is something I enjoy.					
4.	Facts presented in textbooks and lectures usually are correct.					
5.	To do well, it is necessary to compete with other students for the teacher's attention.					
6.	I usually am eager to learn about the content areas covered in class.					
7.	My ideas about content are often as good as those in the textbook.					
8.	Classroom activities generally are boring.					
9.	I enjoy discussing my ideas about the course content with other students.					
10.	Teachers are the best judges of what is important for me to learn in a course.					
11.	It is necessary to compete with other students to get a grade.					
12.	Class sessions typically are worthwhile.					
13.	I study what is important to me and not always what the instructor says is important.					
14.	Very seldom do I become excited about material covered in a course.					
15.	I enjoy hearing what other students think about issues raised in class.					
16.	Teachers should state exactly what they expect from students.					
17.	During class discussions, I must compete with other students to get my ideas across.					
18.	I get more out of going to class than staying at home.					
19.	Most of what I know, I learned on my own.					
20.	I generally feel like I have to attend class rather than like I want to attend.					
21.	Student can learn more by sharing their ideas with each other.					
22.	I try to do assignments exactly the way my teachers say should be completed.					
23.	Students have to become aggressive to do well in school.					
24.	Everyone has a responsibility to get as much out of a course as possible.					
25.	I can determine for myself the important content issues in a course.					

#	Indicator	Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Undecided	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
26.	Paying attention during class sessions is difficult for me to do.					
27.	I like to study for tests with other students.					
28.	Teachers who let students do whatever they want are not doing their job.					
29.	I like to get the answers to problems or questions before anybody else can.					
30.	Classroom activities generally are interesting.					
31.	I like to develop my own ideas about the course content.					
32.	I have given up trying to learn anything from going to class.					
33.	The ideas of other students help me to understand course material.					
34.	Students need to be closely supervised by teachers on all course related projects.					
35.	To get ahead in class, it is necessary to step on the toes of other students.					
36.	I try to participate as much as I can in all aspects of a course.					
37.	I have my own ideas about how classes should be run.					
38.	In most of my courses, I study just hard enough to get by.					
39.	An important part of taking courses is learning to get along with other people.					
40.	My notes contain almost everything the teacher said in class.					
41.	Students hurt their chances for a good grade when they share their notes and ideas.					
42.	Course assignments are completed whether or not I think they are interesting.					
43.	If I like a topic, I usually find out more about it on my own.					
44.	I typically cram for exams.					
45.	Learning should be cooperative effort between students and faculty.					
46.	I prefer class sessions that is highly organized.					
47.	To stand out in my classes, I try to do assignments better than other students.					
48.	I complete course assignments soon after they are given.					
49.	I prefer to work on class related projects (e.g. studying for exams, papers) by myself.					
50.	I would like teachers to ignore me in class.					

#	Indicator	Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Undecided	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
51.	I let other students borrow my notes when they ask for them.					
52.	Teachers should tell students exactly what material is going to be covered on a test.					
53.	I like to know how well other students are doing on exams and course assignments.					
54.	I complete required reading requirements as well as those that are optional.					
55.	When I don't understand something, I try to figure out for myself before seeking help.					
56.	During class, I tend to talk or joke around with people sitting next to me.					
57.	Participating in small group activities in class is something I enjoy.					
58.	I find teacher outlines or notes on the board very helpful.					
59.	I ask other students in class what grades they received on tests and assignments.					
60.	In my classes, I often sit towards the front of the room.					